

ELECTROMAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF COBALT-REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE (CO-RGO)/ EPOXY COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

During the last half decade, graphene, one of the most promising materials at nanoscale, has stimulated extensive scientific interests all over the world. With the extraordinary properties, such as high electrical conductivity (7200S/m²) [2], thermal conductivity (about 5000W/mk) [3], surface area (2630m²/g) [4] and tensile strength (130GPa) [5], this single-layer carbon material is regarded as a significant substitute in fabrication of transistors, integrated circuits, solar cells, chemical sensors and others. Its exceptional properties make this two-dimensional carbon material a promising substitute for other carbon-based materials, such as carbon black, expanded graphite and carbon nanotube, as filler for polymer nanocomposites. And much attention has been paid to synthesize modified graphene or graphene based nanocomposites. As previous studies have proven, graphene can enhance electronic and electromagnetic properties of polymer matrix composites more effectively than other carbon fillers [6].

In our recent work, we synthesized nanocomposites of cobalt nanoparticles decorated on reduced graphene oxide (Co-RGO), endowing graphene with soft magnetism. And we studied electromagnetic properties of polymer matrix composites filled with Co-RGO. Interestingly, complex permeability and complex permittivity of graphene based composites vary in different way as a function of cobalt nanoparticles on graphene sheets.

2 Experimental

2.1 Raw materials

Graphite powder with particle size of 20 μ m (99 wt%) was purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. Potassium permanganate, potassium nitrate, sulfuric acid (98 wt%), hydrogen peroxide (30 wt%),

sodium hypophosphite, palladium dichloride, hydrochloric acid (37 wt%) and ammonia solution (25 wt%) were provided by Beijing Chemical Works. Cobalt sulphate, sodium citrate and stannous chloride anhydrous were provided by Xilong Chemical Co., Ltd. All the reagents whose purity levels were analytical grade were used as received without any further purification. And epoxy resin (E-51) with its curing agent was purchased from Guangzhou Epos Trading Development Co., Ltd.

2.2 Preparation of GO

Modified Hummers' method was employed to produce graphite oxide from natural graphite powder which was oxidized by potassium nitrate and potassium permanganate, at the presence of sulfuric acid [7]. Graphite oxide was prepared from graphite powder by the modified Hummers method using strong oxidants, KNO₃ and KMnO₄, in the presence of sulfuric acid. And then graphite oxide was dispersed in distilled water by ultrasonic exfoliation to produce graphene oxide (GO).

In a typical experiment, 69 mL sulfuric acid together with 1.5g graphite and 1.5g sodium nitrate was first added into a beaker treated with water bath at 40 °C. 9 g potassium permanganate was then slowly introduced into the mixture while stirred by a magnetic stir bar. After reaction for 6h, 120 mL deionized water was added to the mixture and the temperature was subsequently at 60 °C for 30 minutes for further oxidation. Afterwards, the reaction mixture was diluted with 300 mL deionized water. H₂O₂ (30 wt % in water, 4 mL) was then added to remove residual potassium permanganate. The obtained suspension was intensively washed with deionized water by centrifugation and then followed by vacuum drying (80 °C) to obtain graphite oxide powder. Finally, the as-synthesized GO powder was dispersed in the deionized water

forming 100 mL GO suspension (1 mg mL^{-1}), which was treated in an ultrasonic cleaner for 1 h, followed by high-speed centrifugation (3000 rpm, 10 min) to remove impurities, and then a dark brown GO solution was obtained.

Our previous work indicated that slightly raising reaction temperature and extending reaction time on a controllable condition lead to a complete oxidation. After oxidation, graphite oxide was exfoliated to GO via sonication in water. [8].

2.3 Synthesis of Co-RGO

Co-RGO was synthesized by a multi-step electroless deposition process as previously reported [8]. In a typical experiment, 50 ml GO solution was mixed with 7.5 g stannous chloride anhydrous and 10 ml hydrochloric acid (37 wt%), forming a 250 ml yellow colloidal solution and then became black after ultrasonication for 60 min. Redundant Sn^{2+} in solution should be removed by filtration. After filtration, mix 0.15 g palladium dichloride and 20 ml hydrochloric acid (37 wt%) with the black solid to form a 250 ml solution. Keep the above solution under ultrasonication for another 60 min so that absorbed Sn^{2+} ions reacted with Pd^{2+} on the surface of RGO to produce the intermediate, Pd-RGO. Finally, Pd-RGO was added into the 100 ml solution of cobalt sulfate (0.015 mol/L) with sodium citrate (0.035 mol/L), sodium hypophosphite (0.1 mol/L) and ammonia (0.15 mol/L) to complete the deposition of CoNPs. Pretreatment and deposition process were carried out in water bath at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and both the intermediate and final product were washed with deionized water and then dried at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. By varying the initial concentration of cobalt sulfate solution proportionally we can alter the content of cobalt in Co-RGO nanocomposites

2.4 Preparation of Co-RGO/ Epoxy composites

In a typical preparation process of composites, same loading amount (1wt%) of nanofillers (MWCNTs, RGO and Co-RGO with different content of cobalt) were weighed and added into acetone. After that the suspension was under ultrasonication for 1 hour, then resin E-51 was added into the suspension under ultrasonication for another hour. After THF was evaporated out, the mixture blended with curing agent was poured into mould and cured at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour and $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours. Pure epoxy resin

sample was prepared as the control for electromagnetic parameters test.

2.5 Instruments and Measurements

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was conducted with a Rigaku D/max-rB diffractometer using Cu K α radiation. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed with a FEI Tecnai G² F20 microscope equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrometer to perform element analysis. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were obtained by a Multimode Nano4 in tapping mode. Raman spectra were recorded on a LabRam HR800 micro-Raman spectrometer with 514 nm laser excitation. Complex relative permeability and relative permittivity of different graphene/ epoxy composites are tested in the frequency range of 8.2~12.4GHz and 12.4~18.0 GHz by 8722ES vector network analyzer.

3 Results and Discussion

Graphite powder, the raw material, has a layered structure as seen in Fig.1a. After oxidation, the as-prepared graphite oxide maintains similar layered structure. However, in contrast to pristine graphite, layered GO sheets in graphite oxide are heavily oxygenated, manifesting reduced size and damaged layers (Fig. 1b). On the basis of our previous studies on GO, ultrasonication under certain condition would result in complete exfoliation of graphite oxide into mono-layered GO. Because of the presence of hydrophilic groups such as hydroxyl, epoxy, and carboxyl groups on the surface of GO sheets. A mild ultrasonic treatment of graphite oxide in THF results in its exfoliation to form stable dispersions that consist almost entirely of 1-nm-thick sheets, as determined by AFM (Fig.2). Given the uniformity of the observed thicknesses, we believe that these represent the thickness of most exfoliated GO sheets.

Raman spectroscopy is widely used to characterize carbon-based materials especially graphene [9-11]. The two characteristic features are the G band at 1589 cm^{-1} and D band at 1350 cm^{-1} . The D band is ascribed to edges, other defects, and disordered carbon, while the G band arises from the zone center E_{2g} mode, corresponding to ordered sp^2 -bonded carbon atoms [10]. The ratio of the intensity of the D (I_D) to that of G (I_G) band, I_D/I_G , is a measure of the degree of disorder and the average size of sp^2

domain. It is found that the I_D/I_G ratio in graphite oxide (0.842) is much greater than that in graphite (0.245). This increased ratio suggests that the oxidation process results in a higher level of disorder of the graphene layers and an increased number of defects. Besides, a 5 cm^{-1} shift toward a higher wavenumber and a broadened bandwidth of the G-band are found in graphite oxide compared with graphite, indicating a decrease in the in-plane size of graphene during oxidation. Those phenomena are both consistent with the results of some previous reports [11]. Hence, the oxidation of graphite is successful as expected.

In our protocol, it is hydrogen atoms that actually gave their electrons to both metal ions and some oxygen containing groups remained in RGO. In other words, Co^{2+} ions were reduced around Pd seeds, the very catalytic centers help to produce hydrogen atoms. In this way, Co could nucleate and grow upon RGO sheets [8]. The morphology of Co-RGO was observed using TEM. In Fig. 4, Co nanoparticles without conglomeration appear as dark dots dispersing homogeneously on translucent graphene sheets and no free particles outside are observed. Results of particle size analysis tell that the average diameters of nanoparticles are 12.4, 20.7 and 30.5 nm for Co-RGO*1, Co-RGO*2 and Co-RGO*5, respectively. It should be noted that the nanoparticles appear denser and larger as the initial amount of cobalt precursor. The related EDX spectrum of Co-RGO samples (Fig. 5) reveals that C, O, Co, Pd could be detected and a minority of Sn remains adsorbed in the sample because of the extremely high surface area of graphene.

Complex permittivity and permeability (ϵ_r and μ_r) of materials are related to energy storage and dielectric loss and dissipation of the electromagnetic energy. They play a key role in MA performance. In order to evaluate how the added Co-RGO would influence electromagnetic properties of epoxy composites, complex permittivity and permeability of Co-RGO/epoxy at a loading of 1 wt% were measured and are shown in Fig. 6 and 7, respectively. The real part of permittivity of Co-RGO/epoxy composites declines obviously when compared with that of RGO/epoxy composites. The imaginary part of permittivity of Co-RGO/epoxy fluctuates in an irregular way. However, in Fig. 7 the real part of permeability of all composites samples slightly increases with the frequency. Meanwhile the

imaginary part of permeability Co-RGO/epoxy composites is higher than that of RGO/epoxy composites in the measured frequency range indicating that Co-RGO could improve magnetic loss of graphene based composites.

Moreover, the reflection loss of pure resin, CNTs/epoxy, RGO/epoxy, Co-RGO*1/epoxy, Co-RGO*2/epoxy and Co-RGO*5/epoxy composites with different nanofillers at loading of 1wt% are calculated. The reflection loss of a MA layer is estimated by following equations [12-13]

$$Z_{in} = \sqrt{\mu_r/\epsilon_r} \tanh[j(2\pi/c)\sqrt{\mu_r\epsilon_r}fd] \quad (1)$$

$$RL(\text{dB}) = 20\log|(Z_{in} - 1)/(Z_{in} + 1)| \quad (2)$$

Where Z_{in} is the normalized input impedance, c is the velocity of electromagnetic waves in free space, f is the frequency of electromagnetic wave, and d is the thickness of absorber whose value is fixed to 2.0 mm for calculation. Therefore, microwave propagation within electromagnetic media is largely determined by ϵ_r and μ_r of the absorbing materials. The as-calculated results are shown in Fig.8.

As shown in Fig. 8, Co-RGO/epoxy composites, especially Co-RGO*2/epoxy and Co-RGO*5/epoxy, manifest superior microwave absorbing (MA) performance than the composites filled with other nanomaterials. As expected, the MA performance of Co-RGO/epoxy composites shows a dependence on the loading of cobalt: Co-RGO*5/epoxy, with the largest amount of Co added, gives the maximum values of absorption. Although the minor values for reflection loss are not acceptable in practical application, the improved reflection loss, up to 200-300% that of RGO/epoxy, should also be emphasized. The improvement should be primarily attributed to two reasons: on one hand, the substrates for cobalt nanoparticles, RGO sheets, generate electrical loss build a conductive network in epoxy resin; on the other, the added Co improves magnetic properties thus further leading to an increase in magnetic loss. Furthermore, the interaction among metal, graphene and polymer would introduce numerous interfaces in the composites which promote polarization, multiple scattering and reflection and finally generate more dielectric loss. Accordingly, Co-RGO nanocomposites hold great potential in MA application.

4 Conclusions

Adding graphene decorated with cobalt nanoparticles in polymer can enhance both dielectric and magnetic properties of polymer matrix composites at the same time. Complex permeability and complex permittivity of Co-RGO/epoxy composites vary differently in 8-18 GHz. And the values for reflection loss of Co-RGO/epoxy composites are improved significantly, owing to the added Co and the interaction among metal, graphene and polymer matrix.

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Fig.1. SEM images of graphite (a) and graphite oxide (b)

Fig. 2. Typical AFM image of GO exfoliated in aqueous solution

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of graphite (a) and graphite oxide (b)

Fig.4. Typical TEM images of GO(a), Co-RGO*1(b), Co-RGO*2(c) and Co-RGO*5(d)

Fig. 5. EDX spectrum of Co-RGO

Fig. 6. Behavior of real and imaginary part of complex permittivity of different graphene/epoxy composites within frequency range of 8-18 GHz

Fig. 7. Behavior of real and imaginary part of magnetic permeability of different graphene/epoxy composites within frequency range of 8-18 GHz

Fig. 8. Reflection loss curves for composite samples filled with different nanofillers at the loading of 1 wt%